

Non-Linear Finite element analysis of square concrete slabs under shear and flexure

^{1*} C.Chinna Suresh Babu, ²C.Ramachandrudu, ³C.Sashidhar

¹Reacher Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering Jawaharlal Nehru Technical University, Anantapur.

²Professor, Department of Civil Engineering – Chiranjeevi Reddy Institute of Engineering, Anantapur.

³Professor , Department of Civil Engineering - Jawaharlal Nehru Technical University, Anathpur.

*Corresponding author : C.Chinna Suresh Babu

Abstract

The primary focus of this study is an in-depth and exclusive analysis of the structural behavior of square concrete slabs. To achieve this, ABAQUS software has been exclusively employed for finite element analysis. Various slab sizes (750 mm, 1050 mm and 1200 mm), thickness configurations (75 mm, 100 mm and 125 mm), and load positions with different shear-span (a/d) ratios (1.0, 2.0, 2.67 and 3.0) have been ambitiously covered, and a systematic and methodical comparison between traditional steel and innovative fiberglass rope reinforcements has been conducted. This investigation is driven by the well-established and pressing limitations associated with steel reinforcement, particularly its susceptibility to corrosion, leading to a significant increase in maintenance costs over a structure's lifetime. The core focus of this study lies in the a/d ratio (where 'a' signifies the distance of line loads from supports, and 'd' denotes the effective depth of the slab) and its pivotal role in shaping the structural behavior of these slabs. The results, obtained exclusively through computational analysis using ABAQUS, reveal a noteworthy phenomenon: an increase in the a/d ratio imparts a ductile response to the slabs. This response is characterized by increased deformations but concurrently results in a reduction in peak load-carrying capacity, a consequence of a more equitable load distribution. Furthermore, the analysis elucidates that increasing the thickness of the slab precipitates a reduction in peak load-bearing capacity. This phenomenon is attributed to the enhanced rigidity of thicker slabs, which restricts the extent of deformations. Finally, the study underscores the substantial potential of fiberglass ropes to effectively mitigate the inherent limitations of traditional steel reinforcement.

Keywords: glass-fibres, rope reinforcement, steel-reinforcement, square slab, a/d ratio.

Introduction and problem statement

The behavior of square concrete slabs reinforced with steel and fiberglass ropes was examined in this study. The study was prompted by the need to gain a comprehensive understanding of the structural performance of such slabs, given their significance in various engineering and construction applications. One of the primary motivations for this study arises from the limitations associated with conventional steel reinforcement and the potential advantages offered by innovative alternatives, such as fiber glass ropes. Traditional steel reinforcement, while widely used in the construction industry, is not without its drawbacks. One significant disadvantage of steel reinforcement is its susceptibility to corrosion over time. In harsh environmental conditions, steel can rust, leading to a loss of structural integrity and potentially compromising the safety and durability of concrete structures (Dönmez et al. 2017). This corrosion issue often necessitates expensive maintenance and repair measures, increasing the lifecycle costs of reinforced concrete structures. Additionally, the density of steel reinforcement can make concrete structures significantly heavier, limiting their application in situations where weight is a critical factor, such as in aerospace or marine engineering. The increased weight can also affect transportation and handling during construction (Alhilali et al. 2019; Lantsoght et al. 2012; Kang et al. 2021; Parra-Montesinos et al. 2023).

In this context, fiber glass ropes emerge as an alternative reinforcement material that offers a range of advantages over traditional steel reinforcement. These ropes, made from glass fibers, are inherently corrosion-resistant, mitigating the problem of rust and significantly extending the lifespan of reinforced concrete structures. The use of fiberglass ropes not only reduces maintenance and repair costs but also enhances the structural durability and, consequently, the safety of concrete slabs. Furthermore, fiberglass ropes are known for their lightweight properties. Their low density means that they can be used to reinforce concrete without significantly increasing the overall weight of the structure. This feature makes them particularly attractive for applications where weight is a critical concern. In 1994, Tan and Paramasivam thoroughly investigated the punch shear behavior of concrete slabs reinforced with steel fibers. They tested 14 square slabs, each supported along all edges, and applied concentrated loads to the center until failure. The study explored variables including the shear span-to-depth ratio (a/d), steel fiber volume fraction (p_f), slab thickness (h), concrete strength (f'_c), and the size of the load-bearing plate (r). The research unveiled four distinct regions in the load-deflection curve, representing stages from crack initiation to steel fiber yielding and ultimate load. Within the experimental scope, an increase in P_r , h , or r correlated with heightened

punch shear strength and ductility in the slabs, offering potential for performance enhancement. Additionally, the study compared the ultimate punch shear strength with predictions from equations in the literature and code-based equations. The British Standard CP110's equation emerged as a reasonable estimator of punch shear strength, a valuable finding for engineers and designers seeking to enhance the structural integrity of steel fiber-reinforced concrete slabs.

In 2013, a study was undertaken by Cuenca and Serna, to address the challenge of ensuring shear resistance in precast Hollow Core Slabs (HCS), which were traditionally manufactured via extrusion. The solution proposed involved the utilization of fiber-reinforced concrete (FRC). An experimental program was developed, resulting in the production and testing of 26 HCS elements under various conditions. These conditions included different amounts of steel fibers (ranging from 0 to 70 kg/m³) and distinct shear span/depth (a/d) ratios, which took on values between 2.3-4.4 and 8.6. A variety of failure modes were observed during testing, and notable conclusions were drawn. These conclusions highlighted the significant improvement in the shear quality of the material achieved through the incorporation of fibers in the concrete. HCS units with fiber reinforcement exhibited notably higher load-bearing capacities than those without fibers and demonstrated a more ductile behavior. The study emphasized the potential and effectiveness of using fiber-reinforced concrete as a solution to address shear resistance challenges in the production of Hollow Core Slabs through the extrusion method.

In 2018, Change and Seo, explored the replacement of conventional steel reinforcement with fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) bars in concrete structures exposed to aggressive environmental conditions, aiming to address issues like steel reinforcement corrosion and structural deterioration. However, this substitution raised concerns due to the lower modulus of elasticity and non-yielding nature of FRP materials, resulting in significant deflection and wide cracks in the reinforced concrete members. The study sought to establish a suitable design philosophy and reliable methods for predicting the behavior of such structures. To achieve this, they evaluated the behavior of simply supported concrete slabs reinforced with glass fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP) bars in different sizes and reinforcement ratios, examining flexural and shear limit states, pre-cracking behavior, crack patterns, deflections, ultimate capacities, strains, and failure modes. The insights provided hold valuable implications for practical applications and the development of design guidelines for FRP-reinforced concrete structures, making a significant contribution to addressing the challenges associated with this material in concrete construction and enhancing design practices in the future.

Bui et al. 2020 addressed the persistent and intricate problem of shear design in concrete slabs, specifically those lacking shear reinforcement. The study encompassed a dual approach, combining experimental and numerical investigations, with the aim of unravelling the shear behavior of these slabs when subjected to concentrated loads. To achieve this, they employed small but substantial 10 cm thick slabs for testing. Experimental tests provided crucial insights by quantifying the shear strength and revealing the distinct failure modes. The research delved into the influence of various factors, including boundary conditions, the use of four supported side slabs instead of the conventional two, and the impact of varying loading plate lengths. The comprehensive study comprised a series of eight tests on six distinct slabs. Its objectives were twofold: firstly, to assess the applicability and accuracy of shear design formulations in Eurocode 2 and Model Code 2010, utilizing different levels of approximation (LoA I and LoA II), and comparing them to the French approach. Secondly, the study aimed at validating a numerical model through the non-linear finite element method. Impressively, the proposed numerical model closely aligned with the experimental results, providing a robust representation of the slab's behavior. This research not only contributes essential insights into the complex domain of shear design for reinforced concrete slabs without shear reinforcement but also highlights the critical role of combining experimental and numerical methods in addressing this ongoing and challenging issue. Few other studies (Khaja et al. 2013; El-Sayed et al. 2003; El-Sayed et al. 2005) investigated the shear-span ratio on flexural and shear performance of reinforced concrete slabs.

Research methodology and scope

In this study, a parametric analysis using the finite element simulation tool ABAQUS is conducted to investigate the structural performance of concrete slabs (M25 grade) reinforced with both fiberglass ropes and steel (Fe415) under diverse conditions. The study explores variations in the key parameters of the slabs, including their sizes (ranging from 750 mm to 1200 mm), thickness combinations (ranging from 75 mm to 125 mm), and different shear-span ratios (1.0 to 3.0). The objective is to comprehensively understand how these variations impact the structural behavior of the slabs.

To set up the analysis in ABAQUS, the study first entails creating a finite element model of the concrete slabs' geometry, followed by the generation of a mesh that accurately represents the structure. The material properties of concrete, steel, and the unique properties of fiberglass ropes are defined. Boundary conditions are applied to simulate support conditions, with common configurations including simply supported slabs where vertical displacements are constrained and horizontal movement is allowed. Line loads are defined in terms of vertical deflections. The study

also employs ABAQUS's built-in parametric capabilities to establish the parameters to be studied, such as size, thickness, and shear-span ratio.

Figure 1 Tensile stresses in reinforcement (left) and concrete (right) slabs (1200mm size and 75 mm thick) at a/d ratio of 3.0

Upon running the analysis jobs in ABAQUS, the software solves each case with different parameter values. This allows for the systematic investigation of the structural performance of the concrete slabs under a wide range of conditions. After obtaining the results, post-processing is carried out to extract valuable insights, including stress distribution, deformation patterns, and failure modes. This data analysis phase serves to identify trends and relationships between the studied parameters and the slabs' performance.

(c) 125 mm

Figure 2 Load-Displacement relations for different a/d ratios for 750 mm square slabs

Results and discussions

The analysis results, specifically the load-displacement relationships, were obtained through history output. Figure 2(a), (b), and (c) in the findings represent the outcomes corresponding to 750 mm square slabs for thicknesses of 75 mm, 100 mm, and 125 mm. Notably, these results indicated peak loads of 1031 kN, 679 kN, 549 kN, and 528 kN for 750 mm square slabs with 75 mm thickness at a/d ratios of 1.0, 2.0, 2.67, and 3.0, respectively.

a) 75 mm

b) 100 mm

(c) 125 mm

Figure 3 Load-Displacement relations for different a/d ratios for 1050 mm square slabs

The findings revealed a significant and sharp reduction in the peak load when transitioning from an a/d ratio of 1.0 to 2.0. This abrupt drop can be attributed to the change in the load distribution and load-carrying capacity of the slabs. However, as the a/d ratio further increased beyond 2.0, the reduction in peak load became less pronounced. This behavior can be explained by the fact that at a higher a/d ratio, the load is distributed more evenly over the slabs, leading to a more gradual reduction in peak load. A similar trend was observed for slabs with a thickness of 100 mm. This behavior underscores the critical role of the a/d ratio in shaping the structural response of the slabs, as it significantly influences their load-carrying capacity and deformation characteristics. Similarly, the corresponding results for 1050 mm and 1200 mm square slabs are presented in figure 3 and 4 respectively.

a) 75 mm

b) 100 mm

Figure 4 Load-Displacement relations for different a/d ratios for 1200 mm square slabs

Conclusions

The main conclusions from the exclusive non-linear finite element analysis of square slabs under shear and flexure are as follows:

- The a/d ratio, representing the distance of line loads from supports to effective depth, plays a central role in shaping the structural behavior of concrete slabs. It significantly influences load-carrying capacity and deformations.
- An increase in the a/d ratio results in a ductile response in the slabs, characterized by higher deformations, particularly when transitioning from a ratio of 1.0 to 2.0.
- The study highlights a sharp reduction in peak load when transitioning from an a/d ratio of 1.0 to 2.0, primarily due to changes in load distribution and load-carrying capacity.
- Thicker slabs exhibit greater rigidity, which limits deformations but also leads to a reduction in peak load-bearing capacity.
- Fiberglass ropes demonstrate substantial potential as an alternative to traditional steel reinforcement, offering promise in mitigating steel's limitations, such as susceptibility to corrosion.
- The exclusive use of ABAQUS for finite element analysis underlines the significance of computational tools in modern structural engineering research, providing a valuable approach to investigate and understand structural performance.

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